

Diagnostic accuracy of exudative pleural fluid cytology with the correlation of gene xpert in Tuberculosis**Manish Kumar Bhaskar¹, Sunil Kumar², Chand Prakash Jaiswal³, Pawan Kumar Shah⁴, Aashish Gupta⁵**¹Post-graduate (Trainee), Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India^{2,4,5}Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Head of Department, Department of Pathology, Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** Pleural fluid is categorised as either transudate or exudate based on modified Light's criteria. Pleural effusion is classified as an exudative effusion if at least one of the criteria is met. Pleural fluid protein/serum protein ratio of greater than 0.5. Pleural fluid lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)/serum LDH ratio of greater than 0.6. Pleural fluid lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) is greater than 2/3rd of the upper limit of normal value for serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH).**Materials and Methods:** A prospective study was conducted over 21 months at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna. Pleural fluid samples from 130 patients were collected from various departments. Each sample underwent physical, chemical, cytological, and microbiological examinations, including Ziehl-Neelsen staining for acid-fast Bacillus and Gene Xpert testing for Mycobacterium tuberculosis. Demographic information, clinical history, and laboratory findings were documented. Patients with positive Gene Xpert results were monitored on anti-TB treatment for six months, while Gene Xpert-negative patients received a two-week antibiotic regimen. Statistical analyses, including sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values, were calculated.**Results:** Out of 130 pleural fluid samples, 84% were exudates, with a higher prevalence in males (64.55%) and patients aged 21-30 years. Suspected clinical diagnoses included tuberculosis (77.36%), pneumonia (18.18%), and malignancy (5.04%). WBC counts were predominantly in the range of 600-1000 cells/ μ L, and protein levels were above 3 gm/dL in all exudative cases. Cytology showed a predominance of lymphocytes in suspected tuberculosis cases, with a mean of 83%. Gene Xpert detected Mycobacterium tuberculosis in 39.58% of cases, with high sensitivity (86.49%) and specificity (46.43%) for cytological diagnosis relative to Gene Xpert, achieving a diagnostic accuracy of 62.37%. Lymphocyte predominance was significantly associated with tuberculosis ($p < 0.001$).**Conclusion:** Pleural fluid cytology, combined with advanced molecular techniques like Gene Xpert, provides an effective, minimally invasive diagnostic approach for tuberculosis, particularly in resource-limited settings. Cytology demonstrates high sensitivity and negative predictive value, making it valuable in diagnosing tuberculosis and distinguishing it from other causes of pleural effusion.**Keywords:** Pleural effusion, Tuberculosis, Cytology, Gene Xpert, Diagnostic accuracy

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Introduction

Where the visceral and parietal pleurae meet in the lungs, there is an empty space called the pleural cavity. Normally, this hollow space contains a little quantity of liquid that enables these thin layers to move effortlessly over each other. When specific medical issues occur, an excessive amount of fluid might gather in this area, resulting in pleural effusion, which is a sign of an underlying health problem [1]. Pleural fluid is categorised as either transudate

or exudate based on modified Light's criteria. Pleural effusion is classified as an exudative effusion if at least one of the criteria is met:

- Pleural fluid protein/serum protein ratio of greater than 0.5.
- Pleural fluid lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)/serum LDH ratio of greater than 0.6.

- Pleural fluid lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) is greater than 2/3rd of the upper limit of normal value for serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH).

Clinical assessment, imaging studies, study of pleural fluid, and, in some cases, pleural biopsy are the standard methods for diagnosing tuberculous pleural effusion. Diagnostic testing for tuberculous pleural fluid should include cytological, biochemical, and microbiological evaluations of the fluid. In addition to aiding in the diagnosis of tuberculous pleural effusion, it sheds light on the pathogenesis of the condition. Cytology of pleural effusion is the first step in diagnosing pleural effusions. Cytology is a non-invasive and straightforward procedure. It helps the doctor narrow down the possible diagnoses. In addition to providing crucial information for treatment, it may lead to a definitive diagnosis. The cytological analysis's diagnostic precision may be due to the sediment's inclusion of a cell population reflective of a considerably broader surface area than the pleural biopsy [2].

Cytological analysis identifies nearly all adenocarcinomas. Integrating clinical, radiologic, and laboratory results will increase sensitivity [3]. Molecular diagnostics have changed the game when it comes to tuberculosis diagnosis. Molecular diagnostics have increased sensitivity and specificity, and they can identify TB and rifampicin resistance at the same time, which is a huge improvement over traditional approach. One molecular test that has shown resistance in a matter of hours is the Gene Xpert MTB/RIF (Mycobacterium tuberculosis/Rifampicin) test. Even at modest bacterial loads (100–130 bacilli per milliliter of material), CBNAAT can identify mycobacteria [4].

Aim and Objectives

The present study aimed to assess the diagnostic accuracy of exudative pleural fluid cytology in determining the aetiology of pleural effusions and its correlation with Gene Xpert for the detection of Mycobacterium tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: The present study was a prospective observational study and cross-sectional hospital-based study.

Study Place: This study was conducted at the cytology section of the Department of Pathology in collaboration with Department of General medicine, departments of TB and chest, Department of Microbiology and Departments of Biochemistry, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Study Period: The study was carried out from October 2022 to July 2024.

Data Collection: Pleural fluid samples were collected from the Paediatrics, Medicine, Chest, and Tuberculosis Departments, NMCH, Patna. Patient demographic information (name, age, gender) and medical history, including symptoms such as fever, cough, history of upper respiratory infections, tuberculosis status, and family contact history, were recorded. A total of 130 pleural fluid samples were analyzed, categorized as exudates or transudates based on Light's criteria.

Ethical Consideration: The study was approved by the research and ethical committee of the NMCH, Patna.

Inclusion Criteria

- Written informed consent was obtained from each patient before enrolling them in the present study.
- Pleural fluid specimens from all age groups.
- Exudative pleural fluid defined according to the light's criteria
- Sputum AFB-positive patients or sputum gene-positive patients with co-existent pleural fluids.
- The current study included all consecutive patients with pleural effusion on chest radiograph.

Exclusion Criteria

- Transudative pleural effusion
- Pleural effusion from immunodeficient states like HIV/AIDS and those on chemotherapy were excluded.
- The study excluded patients who were unwilling to participate, had a history of bleeding diathesis, empyema, had a minimum pleural effusion that could not be tapped, or had other contraindications to pleural fluid tapping.

Laboratory Procedures

Pleural fluid samples were processed as follows:

1. Physical Examination: Samples were observed for appearance and tested for clot formation.
2. Chemical Examination: Protein and sugar levels were determined in the biochemistry lab.
3. Cytological Examination: Fluid samples were examined using Neubauer chambers for total and differential white blood cell counts. Cytological smears were stained with Leishman and Papanicolaou stains.
4. Microbiological Examination: Samples were subjected to Ziehl-Neelsen (ZN) staining for detecting acid-fast bacilli.

Molecular Analysis (Gene Xpert): Gene Xpert (CBNAAT) testing was performed on pleural fluid to detect Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) and rifampicin resistance. Samples were processed

according to biosafety protocols, mixed with specific reagents, and loaded into Gene Xpert cartridges for analysis. Results were interpreted based on MTB concentration and resistance profile.

Follow-Up and Treatment Response: Patients with MTB detected via Gene Xpert were monitored for six months on anti-TB treatment, while those with negative results received a two-week antibiotic regimen, with clinical and radiological responses assessed.

Statistical Analysis: Data were recorded and analysed by using SPSS software (version 25.0) and Microsoft Excel. Sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values (PPV and NPV), positive and negative likelihood ratios (LR+ and LR-), and other metrics were computed using standard formulas. To compare variables, McNemar's test was used. All comparisons had two tails. Chi-square tests were applied to assess associations, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 1(a): Frequency of eligible cases, age group distribution, and gender distribution of patients

Criteria	Frequency	Percentage
Exudate	110	84%
Transudate	20	16%
Total (Criteria)	130	100%

Table 1(b): Age wise distribution of patients with exudative pleural fluid (n=110)

Age Group (in years)	Frequency	Percentage
0-10	12	10.91%
11-20	14	12.72%
21-30	22	20.00%
31-40	19	17.27%
41-50	12	10.91%
51-60	15	13.64%
61-70	11	10.00%
71-80	4	3.64%
81-90	1	0.91%
Total (Age Group)	110	100%

Table 1(a) shows that the study examined a total of 130 pleural fluid samples, of which 110 (84%) were classified as exudates and 20 (16%) as transudates. Table 1(b) shows age distribution showed

that the majority of patients (60%) were between 7 and 40 years old, with the highest percentage (20%) in the 21–30 age groups.

Table 1(c): Age wise distribution of patients with exudative pleural fluid (n=110)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	39	35.45%
Male	71	64.55%
Total	110	100%

Figure 1: Gender wise ditribution of the patients

Table 1(c) and Figure 1 shows the gender distribution indicated a predominance of male

patients, comprising 64.55%, compared to 35.45% females.

Table 2: Suspected Clinical Diagnosis, WBC Count, and Protein Levels in exudative Pleural Fluid Samples (n=110)

Category	Criteria	Number of Samples (n=110)	Percentage
Suspected Clinical Diagnosis	Tuberculosis	84	77.36%
	Pneumonia	20	18.18%
	Malignancy	6	5.04%
	Total (Diagnosis)	110	100%
WBC Count (Cells/ μ L)	1100 - 1500	17	15.45%
	600 - 1000	83	75.45%
	100 - 500	10	9.10%
	Total (WBC Count)	110	100%
Protein Level (gm/dL)	>3 to <4	28	25.54%
	>4 to <5	60	54.54%
	>5	22	20%
	Total (Protein Level)	110	100%

Table 2, show that in terms of clinical diagnosis, 77.36% of the samples were suspected tuberculosis cases, 18.18% were suspected pneumonia cases, and 5.04% were suspected malignancies. The white blood cell (WBC) count analysis showed that

75.45% of samples had a count between 600-1000 cells/ μ L. Protein levels in pleural fluid samples predominantly ranged from 4 to 5 gm/dL (54.54%), with all exudative samples exhibiting protein levels above 3 gm/dL.

Table 3: Suspected Clinical Diagnosis and Cytological Findings Based on Predominant Cell Type

Suspected Clinical Diagnosis	Total Samples (n=110)	Suspected Cytological Diagnosis	Number of Samples	Predominant Cell	Mean % of Predominant Cell
Tuberculosis	84	Tuberculosis	64	Lymphocyte >50%	83%
		Malignant Effusion	8	Malignant Cell	63%
		Acute Infection	12	Neutrophil >50%	63%
Pneumonia	20	Acute Infection	20	Neutrophil >50%	68%
Malignancy	6	Malignant Effusion	6	Malignant Cell & Lymphocyte >50%	65%

Table 3, show that cytological analysis revealed that among the tuberculosis cases, lymphocytes predominated in 64 samples, with an average lymphocyte count exceeding 50% (mean 83%). For suspected pneumonia cases, neutrophils were pre-

dominant in all samples, with a mean percentage of 68%. Malignant effusions were identified in 6 cases, showing both malignant cells and lymphocyte predominance.

Table 4: Results of AFB ZN Staining, Gene Xpert Detection, and Treatment Response for Pleural Fluids

Test/Response Type	Result	Frequency	Percentage
AFB ZN Staining for Acid-Fast Bacillus (n=96)	Positive	7	6.04%
	Negative	89	94.62%
	Total	96	100%
Gene Xpert for Tuberculosis Detection (n=96)	Positive	37	38.54%
	Negative	56	58.33%
	Error	3	3.13%
	Total	96	100%
Antibiotic Treatment Response in Gene Xpert Negative Cases (n=56)	Positive	55	98.18%
	Negative	1	1.82%
	Total	56	100%
Anti-Tubercular Treatment Response in Gene Xpert Positive Cases (n=37)	Positive	35	94.73%
	Resistance	1	2.63%
	Could not follow up	1	2.63%
	Total	37	100%

Table 4, show that the microbiological analysis showed a low detection rate of acid-fast bacillus (AFB) using ZN staining, with only 6.04% of samples testing positive. Gene Xpert testing for Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) detected MTB in 39.58% of samples. Among the Gene Xpert-negative patients treated with

antibiotics, 98.18% showed a positive response. In the Gene Xpert-positive group treated with anti-TB therapy, 94.73% showed improvement, with only one case of resistance reported. 3 (3.13%) samples that show errors on Gene Xpert patients of these samples were unavailable for follow-up.

Table 5: Correlation of Cytological Diagnosis and MTB Detection by Gene Xpert in Pleural Fluid of Tuberculosis

Cytological Diagnosis for Tuberculosis	Gene Xpert Detected	Gene Xpert Not Detected
Positive	TP = 32	FP = 30
Negative	FN = 5	TN = 26

Table 6: Diagnostic Performance Metrics

Metric	Value
Sensitivity	86.49%
Specificity	46.43%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	51.61%
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	83.87%
Diagnostic Accuracy	62.37%
P-Value	<0.001

Table 6, show that the diagnostic performance metrics indicated a sensitivity of 86.49% and a specificity of 46.43% for cytological diagnosis relative to Gene Xpert, with a positive predictive value

(PPV) of 51.61% and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 83.87%. The overall diagnostic accuracy was 62.37%, with statistical significance ($p < 0.001$).

Table 7: Comparison of Lymphocyte Percentage with Gene Xpert Positivity

Variables	Gene Xpert Positive (Yes) (n=37)	Gene Xpert Negative (No) (n=56)	Total (Mean \pm SD)	P-Value
Percentage of Lymphocyte	80.88 \pm 11.88	50.56 \pm 28.80	64.00 \pm 27.37	<0.001

Table 7, show that a comparative analysis of lymphocyte percentage between Gene Xpert-positive and negative groups revealed a significantly higher lymphocyte percentage in the positive group (mean

80.88 \pm 11.88) compared to the negative group (mean 50.56 \pm 28.80), with a p-value of <0.001, indicating a strong association between lymphocyte predominance and tuberculosis.

Falcon tube

Gene Xpert cartridge

Gene Xpert IV SYSTEM

Monitor

DIAG: - MTB DETCTED

DIAG: - MTB NOT DETECTED

Microbiological Examination: - Pleural fluid samples were submitted to the microbiology section for ZN staining to examine for acid-fast bacilli

Discussion

The present investigation contained 130 cases of pleural fluid, or 84% of the total, and 110 of those cases were exudative in character. The present study did not include 20 fluids (16%) since they were transudate. The incidence of exudative effusion was higher in comparison to transudates, as reported by Sherwani R et al. (2005). The distribution of pleural effusion according to the nature of the fluid was compared with prior studies. The initial stage in diagnosing pleural effusion is determining if it is transudative or exudative. A clear diagnosis and targeted treatment for pleural disease can only be achieved with additional diagnostic techniques, such as cytopathology, pleural biopsy, or even thoracotomy, if an exudative effusion is detected. While treating congestive heart failure, nephrosis, cirrhosis, or hypoproteinemia, therapeutic techniques focused on the pleura are unnecessary if the fluids are clearly transudate [5]. About 60% of patients in the present study fall into the 7–40 age bracket. Twenty-one to thirty-year-olds make up one-fifth of the patients. The age of the patients ranged from 7 years old to 85 years old, with a mean±standard deviation of 37.22±19.83. Patients ranging in age from 21 to 30 made up 20%

of the total. Juvenile patients made up 26% of the total. With an incidence of 15–20% in this age group, Hasseling et al. (2002) also found this [6]. The current study demonstrates that there were more males than females, with 65% of the cases compared to 35%. The 1985 study by Prakash UBS et al. found that pleural effusion was more common in men than in females [7]. The vast majority of the 110 cases of pleural fluid that were studied had a tubercular etiology (77%). Pneumonia was suspected in 18% of cases, and 6% of patients were submitted for cancer cell testing. There was an initial clinical diagnosis of tuberculosis in 57% of the 70 exudative pleural effusion samples studied by Kushwaha et al. (2023). A clinical diagnosis of

cancer has been made in 36% of cases, and 7.0% have been officially diagnosed with pneumonia. The prevalence of pneumonia and cancer is where this study differs from its predecessors [8]. Most of the fluid in the pleura showed a white blood cell count of 600–1100 cells per cumm, found in 75% of these individuals. Between 1100 and 1500 cells/cumm made about 15% of them. Nine percent of the cells were in the 100–500 cell/microliter range. Pulmonary white blood cell count, mean±standard deviation, was 840.82±207.01. The average number of cells in TB pleural effusions was shown to be 764.5 per cubic millimeter in a study by Basu et al. (2012). There was a minimum of 430 cells per cubic millimeter and a maximum of 1,380 cells per cubic millimeter [9].

The presence of protein level in pleural fluids in the present study shows that the protein level of exudative pleural fluids was between the range of 3 gm/dl to 5.6 gm/dl. The majority, 82 fluids (74%), were present between the range of 4 to 5 or >5 gm/dl, and all of them have a protein level >3gm/dl. The result of this study is in accordance with previous studies by Kushwaha et al. (2008), Mario et al. (2005), and Basu et al. (2012). The protein levels in the exudative pleural fluids ranged from 3 g/dL to 5.6 g/dL in the current study, with the majority of fluids between 4–5 gm/dl. This is in agreement with Mario et al., who reported that the protein concentration in exudative pleural effusion is more than 50% of the protein level in the blood [8–10]. The current study demonstrates that out of the pleural fluid samples examined under a microscope for differential count, 64 samples showed a major cell type of lymphocytes, with lymphocyte percentage greater than 50% and a mean lymphocyte percentage of 83%. Our data aligns with the research conducted by Epstein et al., which demonstrated that the majority of tuberculous effusions in their differential count had a lymphocyte percentage over 50%. The neutrophil proportion in these fluids is expected to be less than 50%. In the current investigation, the smears obtained from these

fluids similarly exhibit a higher number of lymphocytes compared to other cell types, with no presence of mesothelial cells. Eosinophils were not found in any pleural fluid smear [11].

In this study, 32 samples of pleural fluid were examined using cytological smear analysis to determine the differential count. The results revealed a predominance of neutrophils, with neutrophil cell count above 50%. In their study, Kushwaha et al. stated that the presence of mainly polymorphonuclear cells in pleural fluid indicated acute pleural inflammation, hence increasing the likelihood of pneumonia with effusion [8]. Out of the 110 samples of pleural fluid that we examined, 14 of them had cancer cells. The cell is malignant and has irregularly shaped and highly pigmented nuclei with noticeable nucleoli. The cytoplasm appears blue and is set against a background of bleeding. Since the initial report by Bennet in 1848 regarding the presence of tumor cells in fluid accumulation, significant advancements over a period of 13.5 years have resulted in the current state of Cytopathological diagnosis of body cavity fluids. Previous investigations indicated that the presence of a high number of lymphocytes and the absence of mesothelial cells in the pleural fluid smear strongly suggested that the origin of the condition was likely tubercular. The present investigation on differential cell counts and cytology of the pleural fluid smear reveals 64 patterns, classified as potentially tubercular in nature. In contrast, 32 fluid samples are considered to be potential cases of acute infection based on the presence of a higher number of neutrophils in the pleural fluid smears. Neutrophilic predominant fluids were sent for gene xpert testing based on the findings of two studies: one conducted by Bielsa S. [12] These studies found that roughly 90% of tubercular pleural effusion cases were lymphocytic predominant, while 10% were neutrophilic predominant. The current study demonstrates that out of a total of 96 samples, only 7 (6.04%) of the pleural fluid samples tested positive for acid-fast bacillus when using Zn staining. The low positive rate is a result of the tuberculous pleural fluid having a little number of bacteria. A bacillary density of 10,000/ml is necessary to detect acid-fast bacteria. In a study conducted by Gopi A. et al. (2006), it was discovered that the detection rate of acid-fast bacilli by Zn staining was less than 10% [13]. Through a meticulously organized meta-analysis, 24 research conducted in India were examined. The sensitivity of gene xpert in Tuberculous pleural effusion was shown to be between 22.7–51.4% when utilizing a composite reference standard (CRS). Prior small-scale studies have shown that the Xpert MTB/RIF test has poor sensitivity, ranging from 15% to 33%, when used on pleural effusion. However, it has demonstrated good specificity, reaching up to 100%. Patients who tested negative for gene Xpert showed im-

provement after 15 days of antibiotic treatment, with 55 individuals reporting symptom improvement. International guidelines advocate for empirical broad-spectrum antibiotics upon detecting pleural infections. Maskell NA, suggested antibiotic therapy for three to four weeks for effective clinical improvement [14]. Mycobacterium tuberculosis was found in 37 out of 93 (39.58%) patients using gene xpert. These patients received anti-TB treatment for six months. Clinical improvement was noted in 35 individuals within four months, with symptoms such as coughing, fever, increased appetite, and weight gain decreasing significantly. The sensitivity of cytological investigation was 86.49%, and specificity was 46.43% compared to gene xpert. The positive predictive value (PPV) was 51.61%, while the negative predictive value (NPV) was 83.87%. Diagnostic accuracy stood at 62.37%, with a significance level of $p < 0.001$. Tetikkurt et al. demonstrated that cytology had a sensitivity of 72% and specificity of 60% for tuberculosis when compared to pleural biopsy, similar to findings in this study [15].

Limitation of the study

A more accurate result could be obtained with a larger number of participants and a multicentric study that includes patients with varying TB burdens. Further testing of diagnostic algorithms across different patient, epidemiological, and geographic groups is also feasible. Cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit studies, as well as its impact on patient care and the detection of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, can all be studied.

Conclusion

This study highlights pleural fluid cytology as a reliable, cost-effective, and minimally invasive diagnostic tool, especially valuable in settings where pleural biopsy is unavailable. Cytological analysis combined with differential cell count proves effective in diagnosing tuberculosis and distinguishing it from malignant diseases. The integration of cytology with advanced techniques like Gene Xpert enhances diagnostic accuracy, with a sensitivity of 86.49% and a high negative predictive value of 83.87%.

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